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ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

D6.3 POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS: SCIENCE-BASED POLICY FOR EU POLICYMAKER

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Executive Summary	Included
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EU-RES	Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	
EU-CO N	Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	
EU-SEC	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document lays the foundations for future discussions within the FOREST (Forum for European Strategy on ICT Standards) committee established by StandICT.eu 2026. The mission of FOREST is to derive for decision makers at the European level a set of focused suggestions and recommendations regarding technology and standardisation for the most urgent challenges in technology domains that are crucial for Europe's future.

This deliverable

1. provides background information on the key stakeholder groups so as to ensure a common understanding
2. outlines the many potential modes of failure in markets/standardisation with a view to suggesting in future reports means of improvement
3. suggests next steps for the FOREST committee when they draft recommendations for policy makers as part of their activities within StandICT.eu
4. recommends specific analyses to clarify obvious gaps in knowledge of the standardisation ecosystem
5. compiles in an Annex a series of tools useful for systematic analysis and presentation

About FOREST: The forum consists of a growing collaboration of standards policy and technology strategy experts from international stakeholders including the EU Chief Standardisation Officer, members from the EC High Level Forum on Standardisation Liaison, the three European Standards Organisations, several National Standards Bodies (NSBs) and Standards Development Organisations (SDOs) and renowned open source organisations. The mission of the forum is to provide a non-partisan source of information and advice to the European Commission (EC) on technological, geopolitical and policy issues. At the heart of FOREST is the goal of end benefit to citizens, found by promoting inclusiveness in advances in our digital economy and society and by offering more transparent and accelerated methods for creating EU Harmonised Standards.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ACRONYM	Explanation
3GPP	Third Generation Partnership Project. A consortium of seven SDOs in the field of mobile telecommunication
AFNOR	Association française de normalization
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANEC	European Association for the Co-ordination of Consumer Representation in Standardisation AISBL
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical standardization
CJEU	Court of Justice of the European Union
DCU	Dublin City University (Project Partner)
EC	European Commission
ECOS	Environmental Coalition on Standards
EEA	European Economic Area (EU states + Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway).
ESO	European Standardization Organization
ESO	European Standards Organisations i.e. CEN, CENELEC and ETSI
ETSI	European Telecommunication Standards Institute
ETUC	European Trade Union Confederation)
EU	European Union (27 member states)
FRAND	Fair, Reasonable and Non-Discriminatory, also Reasonable and NonDiscriminatory (RAND) licensing terms to be offered by the owner of an SEP to standard implementers
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IEC	International Electrotechnical Committee
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IEEE SA	IEEE Standards Association, part of IEEE, best known for developing the IEEE 802.11 standard
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IMCO	EU Parliament Committee on Internal Market and Consumer Protection
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISO	International Standards Organization
ITU	International Telecommunications Union
JRC	Joint Research Centre of the EC
MSP	Multi-Stakeholder Platform on ICT Standardisation
NSB	National Standards Bodies, such as AFNOR and DIN
NSO	National Standards Organisation
SBS	Small Business Standards
SDO	Standards Development Organization (also Standard Setting Organization)
SEP	Standards-essential patent. A patent that is essential to the implementation a standard.
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises. Defined in EU recommendation 2003/3 as enterprises with no more than 250 employees and 50 million Euro turnover
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WTO	World Trade Organization

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The purpose of this document is to create a foundation for future discussions and reports of the FOREST (Forum for European Strategy on ICT Standards) committee regarding policy challenges in ICT standardisation. The mission of FOREST is to derive for decision makers at the European level a set of focused recommendations and suggestions regarding standardisation. Obviously, the recommendations should be presented neutrally and fitted to the decision-making processes of the policymakers (see [1], [2], [3]).

This document is part of a dialogue or collaboration intended to involve all stakeholders in the standardisation process and ecosystem. The first step in a dialogue is to understand the expectations and capabilities of all participants. This document provides an initial overview, to be refined as collaboration goes forward.

Crucial to this is the use of science-based (open and F.A.I.R.) principles and a multi-disciplinary approach. The document is written so as to be suitable for all stakeholders, with significant extra resources included by citing external references (see bibliography). Nobody can be an expert in all areas, but by means of a synthesis of past works and methodologies, it should prove possible to usefully clarify many issues.

This deliverable concisely provides background information useful for each of the foreseen future reports of FOREST:

1. creating a foundation for analysing issues involving standardisation
2. engaging with existing stakeholder activities such as EU projects like StandICT.eu and HSbooster.eu
3. analysing sources of market & system failures in standardisation
4. identifying social, technological, environmental and political trends relevant for standardisation
5. identifying efficient processes for creating EU Harmonised Standards that are fit-for-purpose with respect to EU policies.

The StandICT.eu project is dedicated to improving engagement of stakeholders with the EU standardisation system, by supporting recognised experts in SDO meetings and by providing platforms such as the EUOS (EU Observatory for ICT Standardisation). An early deliverable from StandICT examined how to promote engagement effectively [4], however that document may need updating in future for specific areas of standardisation. StandICT already delivers a stream of ‘landscape’ documents which reference important deliverables from many SDOs in several domains [5]. Moreover, a set of recommendations to the EC has been produced by StandICT.eu partners as a final legacy of StandICT.eu 2023, precursor

of the present StandICT.eu 2026 project. Such recommendations [158] will be further expanded in future policy briefs.

1.2 Challenges for Policy Maker

As every reader knows, Europe and the world are facing tremendous challenges (climate change, energy shortages, sustainability, pollution, population pressure, public health, geopolitics, technological advances in e.g. AI or bio-engineering). Digitalisation is furthermore fusing together various technologies, making ‘horizontal legislation’ essential for policy makers. An insular or modular approach to problem solving cannot cope well with cross-domain issues, nor do ‘vertical’ approaches include the needs, efforts and expertise of all stakeholders.

The range of stakeholders usually considered as part of the standardisation ecosystem includes the European Parliament, the European Council, the European Commission, the EC Joint Research Centre (JRC), EU national governments, special government agencies, European standardisation organisations, specialised standardisation organisations, commercial organisations, advisory groups (commercial, governmental, etc), and subsets of users (e.g. unionised workers, physically disadvantaged persons, consumers), etc.) Naturally, the influential international standardisation bodies (e.g. ISO, IEC, ITU, IEEE) need to be included, as do the larger foreign national standards bodies (such as NIST in the USA). All of these stakeholders have been active since the formation of the European Union, or before.

Each of these stakeholder segments might usefully be further subdivided; for example ‘commercial organisations’ spans global conglomerates with revenues rivalling EU nation states, middle- to small-enterprise companies with a few hundreds or thousands of employees and sales across the whole EU, and innovative start-ups with less than a dozen employees.

Furthermore, modern society also includes stakeholders with more diffuse links to standardisation, such as open source software developers, human rights activists, and also religious groups with deep concerns concerning the impacts of new technologies/standards.

A recent illustration of the multi-stakeholder approach is a call from scientists to create a multi-stakeholder (scientific, industrial, societal, political) group to tackle the global plastics pollution problem, since “[e]ach of these stakeholders have very different characteristics, perspectives, ways of working and responses to the global plastic pollution challenge.” [6]. Responding to citizen concerns, the EU parliament has itself followed a multi-stakeholder and multi-disciplinary approach to waste reduction, drafting new regulations and addressing over 2500 comments, culminating recently in a strong consensus on legislation [7]. Such a ‘systems

thinking' approach has also been advocated and applied in public health planning [8], for example.

The EU Parliament has specifically addressed many challenges related to ICT with a series of strategic programmes, regulations and directives, for example the AI ACT, the Cyber-Security Act [9], the Data Governance Act [10] and the Digital Markets Act [11]. Standardisation is a crucial tool for enabling these regulations.

Furthermore, based on a draft from the EC [12], the EU Parliament has recently reconsidered how to meld such specific efforts into a Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform, better designed to “strengthen European sovereignty and security, accelerate the Union’s green and digital transitions and enhance its competitiveness, reduce its strategic dependencies, favour a level playing field in the Single Market for investments throughout the Union, and promote inclusive access to attractive, quality jobs” [12:29].

1.3 Challenges for FOREST

As stated earlier, the mission of FOREST is to derive for decision makers at the European level a set of focused recommendations and suggestions regarding standardisation in response to policy challenges.

The key questions when deriving recommendations about a given challenge are:

1. what is the challenge and its urgency,
2. who are the stakeholders,
3. what resources/constraints apply to the stakeholders,
4. how do the stakeholders act and interact,
5. what is the desired outcome for the challenge,
6. how can resources/constraints/interactions be used or enhanced to achieve the desired outcome,
7. how can the answers to the above questions be kept balanced and timely.

With limited resources, one challenge for FOREST is the choice between simple and complex methodologies. The simple method is to collect a range of views on a given issue, from a selection of experts, and to report their conclusions and cited arguments. Importantly, results should be presented in ways which lay bare their founding facts and potential sources of bias [13].

Alternatively, a complex methodology might evolve through a series of steps:

1. Choose a focus, either on the most urgent issues, on those where suggestions are lacking, or on those with the greatest long-term consequences.
Note: Most likely the workstreams of the new High Level Forum on European Standardisation [14] will resolve this choice.
2. Choose how to identify and minimise bias in information gathering and in the presentation of conclusions (see e.g. [13])

3. Choose how to interact with stakeholders in an inclusive way, both in evidence gathering and in obtaining critique of the conclusions (see e.g. [15])
4. Choose how to gather evidence and conceptual models of issues, e.g. by consulting experts, by strategic reviews, by surveys, or by leveraging resources of other organisations/stakeholders
5. Choose means of presenting recommendations, either for greatest impact on policy makers or for the most balanced approach, using either academic styles (e.g. publications, webinars) or think-tank styles (e.g. personal meetings, willingness to divert resources to topics chosen by the policy makers)
6. Choose how to validate conclusions and recommendations, e.g. by comparing with contrarian ideas, by comparing with real-world consequences where similar recommendations had been followed, by defining various thought-experiments of scenarios and likely outcomes of the recommendations, etc.

The complexity of the above process is similar in many aspects to that of an Impact Assessment conducted by the EC (see e.g. [15]). It is likely beyond the remit of FOREST.

2. STAKEHOLDERS IN STANDARDISATION

2.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses major stakeholders in standardisation and how they act and interact, as a basis for future analyses of the ecosystem. It is important that all stakeholders note the motivations and constraints in other groups. One of the purposes of this report is to make the facts and/or assumptions about these motivations and constraints explicit and thereby verifiable. An assumption of this report is that the various stakeholders interact with complex interdependencies so that every policy change likely entails a series of collateral effects.

2.2 Standardisation Groups Introduction

Introduction

The StandICT project recently began to survey, as described in the report by Astor Nummelin [16], the rapid evolution of the (European) standardisation ecosystem. Three important trends, and their likely future impact, are under investigation by means of dozens of interviews of experts:

1. Regulatory shifts in the digital domain which have direct and indirect effects on the standardisation landscape.
2. Politicisation of technical standardisation, whereby countries spotlight critical technologies and define standardisation strategies, including integration of (their) ethical principles (often viewed politically), raising concerns about external pressure on standardisation bodies.
3. Growth in importance of ‘non-traditional’ standardisation bodies, for example open source communities or commercial alliances focused on particular technologies.

The first priority in this document is to describe the background of the standardisation ecosystem.

Importance of Standardisation Processes

Standards are at the heart of modern economies:

1. to ensure interoperability between sub-components of complex solutions;
2. to provide buyers, manufacturers and consumers - even across long supply chains - with clear and trusted benchmarks of quality, utility and promised features, and

3. to provide clear conformity criteria or tests, as guarantees of those promises.

It has been concisely summarised in [17] how standards are needed for any trade, even for barter. The practical limitations on government enforcement of standards has shown the need for third party verification: certification of conformance, and for accreditation (audits) of the valid operations of the certification bodies themselves [18:58].

A recent economics survey of six northern European countries from 1970 to 2019, found that standardisation was associated with 25 percent of the growth in labour productivity across 45 industries [19]. This figure is in the mid-range of results reported from other European countries such as Belgium, France, Germany, UK [19:13-14]. Interestingly, the greater share of benefits were realised not by the firms that were undertaking the cost of standardising, but rather by their customers [19:34].

Figure 1: Model of how standardisation impacts economic productivity (from [154:4])

On 2nd February 2022, European Commissioner. Thierry Breton publicly announced [20] a revised standardisation strategy [21] for the EC, emphasising a need for sovereignty and putting European SMEs and the European interest at the centre.

The key issues for EU policy makers and for deployers of any technology are therefore: who sets the standards, what are the constraints and how are they ensured. Based on these factors, the costs (see e.g. [22] re impact on innovation), usefulness or (market) failures can be analysed. The next section considers the standardisation types.

Types of Standardisation Organisations

Standardisation is itself not standardised [23:1370]. The reader is referred to recent overviews or surveys about various standardisation organisations [17] [23] [24] [25] [26].

Figure. 2: Examples of standardisation bodies as surveyed in StandICT report [4]

A report [27] commissioned in 2019 by the Digital Economy Unit of the European Commission Joint Research Centre (JRC) made a case study of 17 major standardisation organisations for ICT and their governance structures, categorising them broadly in terms of their legal/regulatory constraints. The EC provides an introductory web page on standardisation [28].

Academics, lawyers and regulators distinguish three kinds of standards, often using redundant naming:

- 1) committee-based standards (also called "proprietary" standards [23:1370]) that are released within a group/committee of creators/users and which are sometimes enforced by (legal) contract involving certification (e.g. Z-Wave [24], ISO 9001);
- 2) regulatory standards (also called 'government-based' [23:1370]) that are declared by government(s) to be obligatory for given classes of products and services (e.g. Emergency Service eCall [29]);

- 3) voluntary standards (also called ‘private’ [30], ‘market based’ or ‘de facto’ [23:1370] standards) created by consensus and ‘enforced’ by market success (e.g. DECT [31]).

In this document, the term SDO is used in a general sense, to refer to any and all organisations creating any of the above three types of standards.

Voluntary standards ensure compliance by means of (effective) denial of (successful) market access, a significant power in modern economies: after all, direct denial of market access by governments is strongly circumscribed by the World Trade Organisation (WTO) [30] [32] and by many bilateral treaties.

How Voluntary Standards are Created

Most standards development organisations (SDO), and in particular the three European Standards Organisations, have very formal rules for proposing, elaborating, agreeing and publishing standards. At the basic level, however, all SDOs rely on

1. proposals from stakeholders who are members (including the EC)
2. taking into account the state of the art including fundamental research where appropriate
3. elaboration by technical experts within the SDO
4. critique by members and/or external stakeholders
5. publishing of formal documents and/or software.

All of those steps rely on establishing trust between stakeholders (by setting and keeping clear rules [33]) so as to ensure results are valid and accepted. Loss of trust is one of the causes of system failure in standardisation, discussed in a later chapter.

In all of the outputs of standardisation work, success requires avoiding certain risks that:

1. no collaborative standardisation is achieved
2. standards motivated to preserve ineffective technologies are created
3. standards which are unclear or do not bring interoperability for otherwise excellent technology are defined
4. good standards for good technology are found, but are however too onerous/unreliable for testing purposes
5. there are too many (alternative or conflicting) standards.

Motivations of Voluntary Standardisation Organisations

There are many hundreds of SDOs creating voluntary standards (see e.g. [26]). Obviously, there must be some general mechanisms that promote them. The following factors have been suggested [34], most of which are visible in a recent analysis of 70 alliances in the ICT domain concerning why commercial companies, other stakeholders, and governments promote and participate in voluntary standardisation organisations [35:10]:

1. collaboration reduces or distributes the risk when handling complex systems of technologies (which are subject to high risk of failure due to so-called execution risk)
2. collaboration allows a dialogue with stakeholders and customers, allows a common showcasing and critiquing of solutions and reassures that multiple sourcing and a pool of experts exists (aka “no lock-in”)
3. close collaboration is needed when the value proposition requires integration across knowledge elements that are distributed across different stakeholders
4. collaboration may allow a new standards-based ecosystem to be formed, which can unlock large complementarities (aka “creating a bigger cake”) e.g. 3GPP mobile network standards unlocked huge markets in mobile handsets, applications, logistics industries, mobile Apps etc.
5. collaboration allows development of compatible complementary services and promotes widespread consumer adoption, avoiding a situation where firms proliferate incompatible technical alternatives to solve the same end user problems

Standardisation is also more likely when there is competition to define a platform or framework in the marketplace [36]. Such competition is particularly strong when it is believed that a framework will significantly impact existing productivity, especially if a network effect is considered probable. Therefore these additional motivations for cooperation may apply to SDO members:

6. cooperate to avoid huge replication of development and marketing activities, in the case that firms hold similar knowledge foundations
7. cooperate to try to gain early mover advantage by being the first to deploy major aspects of a framework
8. cooperate to help define (or at least be well-informed concerning) the specifications and benchmarks which will later be mandatory (in the case of regulatory standards) or be de facto requirements for deployment of products and services
9. cooperate to try to be the main developer/supplier of the main interfaces of the platform
10. cooperate to compete with and challenge an established SDO ecosystem, (assuming this is permitted by relevant anti-trust laws)
11. cooperate to establish a market for technologies, such that specific patents are essential in order to comply with the standards (so-called SEP, standards essential patents) and which therefore become particularly valuable
12. cooperate to generally share information, in the cases that:
 - there are no lucrative downstream product streams to protect
 - technology sharing, development and validation is seen to reduce risks or costs.

It should be noted that within a standardisation organisation any specific standard may encounter complex changes in the level of support. Standards are continually

going out of favour and being replaced as technology or markets evolve. For that reason, motivations of stakeholders may vary across time, so they might:

1. initially support a standard in an SDO (including i.a. NSOs and NSBs)
2. then perhaps desire to extend it (to be more attractive to users, or to disadvantage competitors, or to acquire effective control of the architecture, etc) [186]
3. then perhaps desire to withdraw from a common standard if it commoditizes their core business [37] or if end-users find it unsatisfactory
4. then perhaps desire to return to support it again if their business shifts to complementary products [38:14] (most especially, to services based on the standard).

There is a large range of technical standardisation organisations for ICT, and their work may sometimes be either invisible or opaque to many societal stakeholders or policy makers. SDOs are active at national (e.g. DIN, AFNOR), European (e.g. CEN, CENELEC, ETSI) and global (e.g. ISO, IEC, ITU-T, IEEE, W3C) levels. They can all receive inputs or comments from government, corporate, alliance and educational sources. Each SDO has their own focus, their own rules of governance, and their own deliverables (recommendations, interface descriptions, testing specifications, etc).

A partial list of organisations, with abstracts and internet links, of about 400 SDOs and over 500 ‘influencer’ groups which do not themselves develop standards, has been compiled as an excel file during the creation of this report, to be expanded as appropriate in future reports. An interactive mindmap version is publicly available [39].

That partial survey dramatically illustrates the key difficulty for stakeholders, in determining which organisations are doing work relevant to them and/or where they should input comments or results. For cross-domain topics, such as pollution or artificial intelligence, the number of relevant organisations is huge. Many of them are expensive to join, or they keep documents confidential behind paywalls, or they have restrictive membership selection criteria.

Some organisations strongly avoid initiating work on topics already established in other groups, which they say helps avoid fragmentation and creation of conflicting standards. It also offers an advantage for those members that have sufficient resources to join multiple SDOs, because the organisation does not need to send the same staff to multiple groups. However, SDOs composed of mainly SMEs or of individual members may prefer to set up new sub-groups within their ‘home’ SDO whenever there is need, so that members are not forced to join multiple SDOs. Even ‘insiders’ of the standardisation ecosystem rarely interact with more than a few groups, however, so it is very difficult to build a coordinated cross-domain approach

2.3 Policy Makers

Introduction

Policy makers for standardisation at the national and European level seek to mediate - especially in the realms of health, safety and market transparency - between societal concerns, markets and innovation.

Scientists, engineers and standardisation experts, however, often prefer to pretend that their technical work is “orthogonal to” issues of politics, social values, or indeed survival of their culture or even the human race. That makes things simpler. Unfortunately, that is not always true, and standards and standardisation can have a huge impact on human values, in the long term or even the short term.

Policy makers recognized this long ago and standardisation became a tool for all the usual aspects of government: monitoring of illegal behaviour, influencing trade, training and education in technology, promoting economic success, constraining dangerous commercial practices, etc. The question for governments (and every individual expert) is therefore: what aspects of standardisation benefit their chosen human values, which aspects put those values at risk?

Those benefits and risks may also be strongly influenced by the copyright or other intellectual property rights asserted for obtaining a copy or using the standard, or obtaining certification (including certification of software) for products using the standard. Details of IPR filings (e.g. for patents filed decades earlier) may critically affect how later standards can be used commercially and policy makers may need to consider that.

Within the EU, and also at national level, there are quite a range of different mechanisms whereby voluntary standards may be cited in regulations and laws, becoming regulatory standards [40]. Additionally, the verification of compliance with those standards may require a range of certification and accreditation mechanisms and standards [41]. Every year the EC issues an Annual Work Programme listing and prioritising various topics [211] where further voluntary standards are recommended.

Due to the very rapid pace of technological development in ICT, governments have difficulty in defining technical standards in a timely way. They have progressively turned towards leveraging of voluntary standards. In the last decade, a desire to leverage ICT and related standards to enhance the “Brussels effect” [42], whereby clear regulations within the huge market of the EU serve as a baseline globally, may also have become a consideration for politicians [74].

During the EU Parliament open session in January 2023 of the IMCO hearing on Standardisation in the Single Market, the issue was highlighted of how to prioritise EU interests, while keeping good international cooperations with democratic

partners [43]. Scientific analysis of an open strategic autonomy (OSA) concept is proceeding [44]. Likewise, policymaking is proceeding apace for our global trading partners, the USA, Japan, China, India, etc, so Europe needs to maintain a multilateral balance.

At the level of the European Union, a key instrument for leveraging standardisation to ensure that policy decisions positively impact society has been the New Legislative Framework [45].

New Legislative Framework

The EU introduced the NLF (New Legislative Framework) in 2008 [45], which by now consists of two regulations (which apply across the EU immediately upon ratification) and a directive (which requires the EU national members to transpose them to equivalent national legislation). Directives should be officially transposed within about two years, on average however require much longer. There is an overview for the public on a dedicated EC website [46].

The purpose of the NLF was (and is) to improve surveillance of product safety, clarify how products can be certified according to technical standards for EU-wide sale, and create a reusable ‘toolbox’ of legislative methods to improve consistency. The NLF, initiated nearly 20 years ago, fundamentally assumes certain marketplace actors and roles, for example ‘manufacturers’, which may need re-examining in the light of trends such as the growth of open-source software and the expanded role of giant global technology companies (none of which have a European base).

The dedicated EC website lists 24 areas, from toys to medical equipment, where complete alignment has been achieved. The EC completed in November 2022 a review, including substantial stakeholder feedback, of the New Legislative Framework and found that results were good, but some changes would be worthwhile [47]. The report lists statistics on the numbers of ENs created, and the (few, but significant) cases where the work was not achieved.

A keystone of the NLF is that manufacturers can self-certify products that claim conformance with relevant harmonised European standards (listed here [48]), which is then treated as equivalent to conformity with the related product regulations (“presumption of conformity” [49]). Companies that are discovered to lie about this face strong penalties. This approach has greatly accelerated the EU Single Market, accompanied however by complex testing and accreditation processes [50] [51] and relying on the three European Standards Organisations (CEN, CENELEC and ETSI) to publish suitable harmonised European standards (officially known as European Norms) in a timely manner.

The main mechanism to create harmonised European Standards is by means of the EC reacting to an Act or Directive of the EU Parliament, by making a (funded) Standardisation Request (SR) to one or more of the three ESOs to create certain

specifications conformant with, and needed by, an EU Act or Directive. Those standards, insofar as they are eventually vetted by the EC, are then cited in the Official Journal of the European Union (OJEU) [52].

According to a report of the EC [53:6], 44 SRs were issued in the period 2015-2022, of which six requests were not accepted by the ESOs (2 thereof by ETSI). ETSI typically is requested by the EC to complete about 10 Harmonised European Norm in ICT per year. Grounds for not accepting a standardisation request are generally: inability to meet the requirements; perceived lack of need for one or more technical specifications; disagreement with deadlines set for the delivery. The 38 agreed SRs resulted in the submission to the EC during 2018-2020 of 1009 specifications as hENs [53:7], thirty-four of those by ETSI and the other 97% by CEN/CENELEC.

One of the weaknesses of the NLF system is the gap in time between political goals (the product regulations, which typically provide for a two-year transition phase) and the speed of creating suitable conformity specifications (which at best requires 18 months and may need two or three times as long). This gap only increases as technology becomes more complex, or when it begins to enter the market even before fundamental research has been completed (example: ChatGTP). In such cases, the policy makers' mission to protect citizens' rights and safety comes into direct conflict with the standards organisations' mission to provide reliable specifications.

If national governments and/or regulators in the EU choose to declare some voluntary standard to be mandatory by law, or request that voluntary standards be created specifically in order to fulfil regulatory needs, e.g. all Harmonised European Norms [54], by a process described in [55] then those voluntary standards become regulatory standards. Strictly speaking, Harmonised European standards are not mandatory, because manufacturers do theoretically have alternative options to demonstrate compliance with the requirements of the relevant EU Acts, Regulations or Directives. However, the administrative delays and costs of the alternatives are usually extremely unattractive.

There is a valid political concern that, by endorsing standards created by non-government agencies, the door is opened to so-called "policy capture" [25:59]. In the recent example of the AI ACT, it has been argued that while the Act sets high-level requirements, the contents of harmonised standards will provide a much more precise interpretation of specific requirements and their practical implementation [56:12]. However, by exclusively reserving to itself the "essential requirements" (objectives) for its EU Acts and Directives and by delegating the "technical requirements" (the means) to the ESOs (European Standards Organisations, i.e. CEN, CENELEC or ETSI), the EU Parliament and the EC are actually *less* at risk of policy capture [25:72].

For many years harmonised European standards were considered to be secondary to the primacy of the law, however in 2016 the European Court of Justice decided

in a court case James Elliott Construction Limited vs Irish Asphalt Limited [57] that in some sense those mandatory standards become equivalent to law.

That Elliott Case decision has been contested in some national legal systems [58], and is also not endorsed by the European Parliament [59:3], and is subject to review in the CJEU [60], but currently the European Commission considers [61:3] that it has a legal duty to verify the suitability of all Harmonised Norms. The EC therefore funds consultants to participate in the development of the Harmonised Norms in order to ensure that endorsement can be achieved in a timely manner - so-called Harmonised Standards (HAS) consultants [62] [63]. However, even hiring of substantial numbers of HAS consultants (increased 50% to 3400 person-days in 2023 [64]) is not a guarantee of success.

One of the most urgent issues is to bridge the gap between important socio-political requirements for safety, privacy and sustainability, and the reality that in many use cases (e.g. cyber-security or artificial intelligence) the risks and means of mitigation are extremely difficult to form into testable specifications. This gap leads to delays while ongoing research is adapted, as well as the possibility that specifications will be evaluated as not fulfilling the requirements of the relevant Standardisation Request.

There is also another thread of case law where it is argued that any standard or specification “included by reference” into a law must be available free of charge to citizens. A position paper by CEN/CENELEC in 2017 argued, however, that the Elliott Case decision specifically excluded documents from the three ESOs from such cases [65:3]. A definitive ruling of the European Court of Justice (ECJ) is expected by the end of 2023 (see [60]). ETSI standards are in any case available on the internet at no cost.

Identifying efficient processes for creating EU Harmonised Standards

The European Standardisation System for ICT has been extremely successful and has been much admired at various times from other nations (see e.g. [66]). The European Parliament and the EC have periodically reviewed and revised its operation, most recently in early 2022 [67]. The economic, ethical and political pressure to ‘improve’ it, in these challenging times, is huge.

However, successful and timely standardisation relies on the smooth collaboration of thousands of people, across dozens of different organisations, where changes of processes can trigger delays, uncertainties, doubts of legitimacy and loss of trust. For that reason, recommendations for changes should be evidence-based, gradual, and derived after a thorough review of the literature as well as carefully prepared interviews with stakeholders.

There are a number of recent reports (e.g. [68] [69]) and think-tank outputs (e.g. [70]) which could be used to launch a systems-based analysis. Each of the European Standardisation Organisations has issued their own recommendations.

ETSI, for example, continuously reviews its mission, focus and governance. It commissioned an external review in 2019 called "The Bildt Report" [71], which examined ETSI's role in European and global standardisation and in collaborations with the EC. A follow-up report from ETSI published one year later made several dozen recommendations [72].

Soft Law

There is a range of literature expressing concern that governments will (or already do) use voluntary standards to achieve political goals, going even beyond what they can achieve by legislation [25:58] [73] [74] [75] [76]. Successful voluntary standards that are found to be supportive of government policies are sometimes referred to as 'soft law': this usage can be confusing and should be avoided. Another usage of 'soft law' is clarified in [77], and is used in [78] for example to analyse governance of AI deployments.

It is true that 'soft law' is sometimes defined as "a program that creates substantial expectations that are not directly enforceable by the government" [79], which is indeed one way of looking at voluntary standards. However, much more strict definitions and examples have been provided in a seminal paper by Fabian Terpan in 2015 [80] and by later scholars, showing soft laws to be "norms which define both an obligation and a form of enforcement which fall short of legal enforcement". The more clear the obligation, the more direct and unavoidable the enforcement, the more 'hard' is the norm, particularly if the obligations are set by agencies which actually often also create 'hard' norms.

There is a range of academic research showing, even using this stricter definition, that 'soft law' is indeed a large body of material within the EU [76] and is increasing [74] [75]. Some EC-funded research on this topic was hosted at www.solar-network.eu, until October 2019, whereby an archived set of results is available [81].

The EU is usually characterised as a region where the "Treaty on European Union enshrines the rule of law as one of the fundamental values of the EU" [82]. Therefore, the growth in cases of 'soft law' should be carefully monitored by stakeholders and in any case should be considered as a factor in policy activities.

2.4 Societal Stakeholders

It was implicitly assumed in the above descriptions of the standards ecosystem that industry partners would debate and create the technical standards according to their commercial priorities, while politicians and political organisations would seek to protect the interests of societal stakeholders (consumers, small businesses, sub-groups of society such as employee unions, citizens who are physically or financially disadvantaged, etc.).

This assumption has become increasingly questionable as ICT standards impact stakeholders beyond a single nation and with unintended or even unpredictable consequences (e.g. impact of 3GPP location services on ride hailing, use of Bluetooth for Covid-19 contact-tracing with potential invasion of privacy).

Therefore, in the EU, ongoing input to and critique of standards and standardisation processes, directly made by societal stakeholders, is increasingly expected and promoted by politicians. A particular example is the creation by the EC in September 2022 of the High Level Forum on European Standardisation which is empowered to “bring together high-level representatives of up to 60 members consisting of stakeholders from EU/EEA countries, European standardisation organisations, industry, civil society and academia, to discuss how to improve the European standardisation system” [14]. Besides Expert Groups (of which more than a thousand have been registered by the EC to date [83]), other methods of stakeholder consultation have been extensively used and critiqued [84] [85].

User groups or societal stakeholder organisations may feel buffeted by the techno-economic forces augmented by the standardisation ecosystem, and therefore be motivated to participate in standardisation. Correspondingly, no members of the standardisation ecosystem can ignore the political or societal ‘backlash’ when technical choices are found to be bad. Diesel car motors and incorrect certification of pollution limits is perhaps a familiar example [86]. The societal stakeholder organisations therefore often have direct mandates from their members to attempt to monitor and influence standardisation. See for example ANEC’s preliminary views on the draft Annual Union Work Programme (AUWP) for European Standardisation for 2023 [87].

The EU Parliament recognized in 2012 that a number of types of societal stakeholder organisations are particularly important stakeholders in standardisation, the so-called Annex III organisations, the criteria for which are listed in Annex III of Regulation (EU) No 1025/2012 [88]. Currently the following four organisations are recognized (and partially funded by the EC) under Annex III:

- ANEC (Association Normalisation Européenne pour les Consommateurs) for consumers' interests
- ECOS (Environmental Coalition on Standards) for environmental interests
- ETUC (European Trade Union Confederation) for workers' interests
- SBS (Small Business Standards).

Even as pan-European organisations, however, it is practically impossible within the limited resources of the above organisations to have delegates with appropriate expertise in all of the standards activities that strongly affect their members. This is an issue that all stakeholders agree needs improvement [89].

In addition to the above ‘big four’, dozens of other stakeholder and lobby groups may need to be considered as part of the standardisation ecosystem, depending on the topic area, for example in the case of sustainability and climate change.

A report [89:4] to CEN/CENELEC cited a number of barriers when Annex III organisations try to access standardisation: e.g. significant participation fees, requiring individual memberships, diverse meeting locations or languages [89:2]. Of particular concern to the Annex III organisations, in the framework of CEN/CENELEC, and particularly for harmonised standards, was the “growing share of transposed international standards, in some sectors over 70% (caused by the principle of ‘primacy of international standards’ and legal agreements with ISO and IEC)” whereas the Annex III organisations have no right of participation in those international standards bodies (ISO [90], IEC [91]).

The Annex III organisations noted also the lack of “tools to be able to identify those work items (WI) and standardisation initiatives relevant to SMEs, trade unions, consumers and environmental interests” [89:3]. A lack of influence was noted “when counting heads for consensus” which ignores the size of the constituency. It was recommended that “[o]pinions, appeals and sustained objections are duly noted and considered by CEN and CENELEC and communicated ASAP to the European Commission, in particular, in the case of harmonised standards”. It was noted that ESOs should be more aware that the Annex III organisations are each representing a distinct constituency and as such must be differentiated i.e. one delegate cannot represent another organisation in policy or technical work [89:6].

They also suggest that much better inclusiveness could be achieved through proactive steps by ESOs, for example: actively invite Annex III experts to contribute to relevant work items; prioritise holding of hybrid meetings; provide timely translations of key documents; allow persons from Annex III organisations to chair committees; actively monitor inclusiveness challenges and opportunities in the ESO; assign ESO budgets for actions (for example through projects) on inclusiveness in close cooperation and with the agreement of Annex III organisations. Regarding inclusiveness, see also the European Economic and Social Committee report [92].

In summary, the other stakeholders agree that societal stakeholders should participate and collaborate on standards making, however resources and expertise to do so is lacking and SDOs’ existing processes often make participation prohibitively difficult.

2.5 Research Institutions

Research institutions (academic, corporate, governmental, etc) are obviously fundamental stakeholders in advances in ICT, but cannot be covered in depth in this report. They are also not the only sources of innovation. Individuals may still exert influence (e.g. Linus Torvalds, initiator of the LINUX open source software movement) as may societal stakeholder groups (e.g. the Wellcome Trust non-profit organisation for funding medical research, based in the UK). An open-source Citizen Science approach is increasingly contributing to e.g. environmental studies [93]. Each of these segments have differing goals, resources and operating methods.

Monitoring and promoting research activities is a key aspect of national strategic programmes, because of their positive impact on national economies and global influence, as shown by historical examples such as the DARPA (Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency) programme of the USA, or by the German Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft.

Regarding the conversion of fundamental research into engineering and thence into standardisation activities, with significant economic and societal impact, the EC has long funded alliances of research partners (e.g. the Horizon Europe programme) and more recently has encouraged so-called dissemination into standardisation by means of funding multi-year alliances and agencies to assist the process (e.g. EISMEA [94], KVP [95], HSBooster.eu, stand4eu.eu, etc.).

How then can FOREST contribute to suggesting how to improve the alignment between EU policy, research activities and impact on standardisation? So much has already been written on these topics, including specifically from single stakeholder viewpoints as well as meta-analyses, that the first step must be an inventory or landscaping report to understand current best practice. Focusing on a single research theme where EC funding has significant influence would improve the chance of making effective recommendations. Therefore, the FOREST committee could scope the analysis by choosing a theme from the overlap of EU research policy, the EC standardisation work plan [21] and the policy priorities of the European Parliament.

3. SOURCES OF MARKET & SYSTEM FAILURES IN STANDARDISATION

3.1 Introduction

The following sections briefly treat some potential sources of market and system failure related to standardisation, at a general level (see also [15] and [96]). More focused domain-specific analyses are needed for future documents in specific technical areas. Readers should note that there are no perfect regulatory/market solutions [97].

All of the factors below can lead to gradual or sudden collapse of efficiency in the market, and the deployment of inefficient (or too many) technologies and standards.

3.2 Standardisation Failures

For ‘traditional’ standardisation, the standardisation expert Carl F. Cargill wrote in 2011 a seminal paper entitled ‘Why Standardization Efforts Fail’ [98], which concisely characterised the fallible human nature of standardisation in the following words:

“It should be remembered that a participant in a standardization effort wears many different hats simultaneously—hats that cover professional pride (doing what’s right), corporate or organizational goals (doing what’s right for your company), standardization organizational goals (doing what’s right for the organization and in scope or charter and following the rules), a national interest (doing what is right for your country’s industrial, social, or legal policies), and personal friendships (doing what’s right to make you feel good and for social and professional strokes). When you put two dozen people with conflicting emotions, goals, backgrounds, and personal motivation in a room, ask them to decide on a complex interface whose future characteristics may or may not impact the market, and then provide minimal guidance and no enforceable deadline, one is hard pressed to describe the outcome as a rational economic decision.” [98]

Many case studies and extensions based on Cargill’s descriptions of failure modes have been published [99].

Cargill examined the failures in the life cycle of standards (Pre-conceptualization, Conceptualization, Discussion, Writing and Implementation) as follows:

1. The standard fails to get started.
2. The standards group fails to achieve consensus and deadlocks.
3. The standard suffers from “feature creep” and misses the market opportunity
4. The standard is finished but the market ignores it.
5. The standard is finished but implementations are incompatible.
6. The standard is accepted but is used to manage [control] the market.

Approximately a page of concise explanation is given for each issue, with references [98].

Three further systemic issues are the break-down of modularity, the proliferation of SDO groups and the breakdown of trust.

Modularity of solutions allows deconstructing a large problem into many smaller ones which can be solved separately and efficiently. In software this often means creating separate software functions with defined interfaces, or (preferably) re-using existing ones. In standardisation it often means first defining requirements, then an architecture of modular systems, then the functionality of each module. Unfortunately, cross-domain problems often are not solved efficiently in this way because maximising efficiency in one module may worsen results in another. For example, decades of developing efficient battery technologies have resulted in batteries containing cadmium, lead, zinc, manganese, nickel, silver or mercury, all of which are difficult to dispose of safely.

The proliferation of SDO groups (due to variance in languages, nation states, missions, costs, etc) means that a significant number of groups work on similar topics, making discovery and selection of a suitable group difficult. A range of groups may be beneficial in allowing various approaches to be examined in depth by enthusiastic proponents rather than ‘debated to death’ in a larger group. It also may allow grouping of members who have a common motivation and level of trust, or a common style of solving problems, allowing faster development. Unfortunately, digital technologies have not yet solved the problem of obtaining and retaining an overview.

The breakdown of trust is a well-defined failure mode in all social contracts, including standardisation. Several references have been provided earlier in this document. Multi-player game theory analyses of sequential interactions show marked advantages when ‘quid pro quo’ is accepted and honoured. Recent statistical analyses show that trust also positively impacts market efficiency [100].

Additionally, there are many failures based on human nature and social interaction which lead to delays or collapse of collaborative work within a standardisation group. They are expressed here alphabetically and in colloquial terms since they are so common:

- ASSume - To assume = make an ass out of u and me.

- Two different stakeholders typically do not completely understand the constraints and motivations of each other, but make assumptions.
- A common assumption is that, because an idea is simple, implementing it within the other's administrative structure will also be simple.
- Another assumption, long disproved but still common, is that cyber-security protections can be added near the end of the development of ICT specifications.
- KISS - Keep it simple, stupid.
 - The acronym expresses a desire to avoid unnecessary complications, however the real world is full of *necessary* complications, in particular in cross-domain problems. In such cases, KISS can lead to specifications that are unworkable.
- NIH - Not invented here.
 - SDO groups may not dedicate the time to understand the paradigm of relevant other standards and instead create their own specifications using concepts with which they are more familiar.
- NMP - Not my problem.
 - An SDO group might be the most suitable place for stakeholders to contribute on an issue, but the SDO may reject the input because it is at the fringe of their scope or else requires changes in their timeplan.
- TL;DR - Too long, didn't read.
 - Converting 800 pages of technical specification into an interoperable solution is a daunting task. Adding "one small change" may be a large effort not supported by the majority of members. Converting over 100 pages of requirements from a Regulation into a series of technical specifications is even more daunting.
- TMI - Too much information.
 - Surveying the state of the art and the key standardisation bodies to discover if relevant solutions already exist can be so daunting that stakeholders decide to create their own specification instead.

All of the above failure modes can be influenced, for better or for worse, through government interventions. An updated report in 2010 by Swann [101:29-38] is an excellent entry point to the literature.

3.3 Patent Lock-out and Lock-ins

Prior to the creation of a legal protection for (industrial) intellectual property rights (IPR), inventors and manufacturers simply attempted to keep key aspects of their processes secret as long as possible in order to maximise profits. That hindered innovation. The patent system was developed in order to make those technical advances visible to all, while retaining licence protection in the market. Within the field of ICT, with its huge benefits of economies of scale, SDOs and governments began encouraging licensing based on FRAND (fair, reasonable and non-discriminatory) for standard essential patents (see [27] [66] [102]).

Nevertheless, there are huge market inhomogeneities and many ICT processes rely on IPR which is held by relatively few companies, or in jointly administered ‘patent pools’ (see [103]), which leverage this to extract market advantages [104].

3.4 Sub-optimal Governance

The rules of governance of SDOs, including the rules for admittance of new members and for participation by non-members, differ. All rules are a balance of costs (administrative overheads, time and travel requirements, timeliness of decisions, etc) vs benefits (transparency, inclusivity, planability, etc). Research on the impact of these governance rules on SDO operations is relatively sparse (see reviews [24] [27] [34] [105]).

The importance of trust in multi-party alliances, as an informal glue supporting formal rules [106], is well known [105] and fragile [107]. There is a human tendency that, the more that the formal rules are emphasised, the more some partners may wonder about trustworthiness: after all, “where there is smoke, there is fire”, or “when it is possible to fully trust a partner, there is no need to control its behaviour.” [106:495][4]

Therefore, problems in governance may make standardisation slow, intransparent or fragmented.

3.5 Market Inefficiencies

In ICT, the vast majority of standards are voluntary standards. Initially there may be a significant number of different standards for a particular purpose, developed by different segments of the technology ecosystem, however nowadays the strong impact in ICT of ‘network effects’ [108] [109] generally results in one or two clearly dominant approaches, and the definition of some technical means of interworking.

Various economic and game-theoretic factors (e.g. ‘first mover advantage’, ‘winner takes all’, ‘switching costs’) may result in a standard succeeding in the market that is sub-optimal, either technically or economically [110] [111]. The example of the QWERTY keyboard is often given for this kind of success, the generic name for which is ‘path dependence’.

These factors, and a number of others, have been cited over 20 years ago by Swann in a report to the UK government [112], and in hundreds of later articles citing that report. A key presumption of Swann was that “[i]t is recognised, however, that while the existence of market failure may be a necessary condition to justify government involvement, it is not a sufficient condition. A second

necessary condition is that government is capable of intervening to improve matters.”

That is a key constraint on future recommendations of the FOREST committee, to evaluate whether a limited number of suggested government initiatives can reduce any identified market inefficiencies with a reasonable cost/benefit ratio.

3.6 Market Externalities

The technical standard most widely supported in the market may not take account of externalities, i.e. costs or benefits of an activity that are experienced by an unrelated third party, e.g. pollution after disposal of nickel-cadmium rechargeable batteries. Externalities are one reason for governments to promote or enforce one standard over another.

3.7 Unclear Liability

Product liability is governed in general by the EU Directive 85/374/EEC published in 1985 and currently under revision [113], as well as numerous domain-dependent (e.g. for health) regulations. However the EU parliament determined that the situation for Artificial Intelligence required a domain-independent (horizontal) approach and the EC made in September 2022 a proposal [114] for a Directive on AI Liability that has not yet been agreed. The impact of the directive would be large. Several commercial websites are devoted to considering it (see e.g. [115]).

For all stakeholders, it may be a matter of concern that under EU law there is almost no chance that a SDO could be found legally liable for harm/neglect caused through creation of inefficient or unsafe standards i.e. SDOs could not be sued for negligence [116].

4. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable, addressing issues within the scope of the FOREST committee, has outlined the breadth of relevant institutions (illustrated by [117]) and some of the difficulties the main stakeholders (societal, standardisation, research, business, policy) encounter. Some areas touched upon in this document will undoubtedly be covered in more depth as part of future reports.

It is hoped that the background information provided will be useful for future deliverables, which should preferably be focused on a single key issue in order to reduce complexity in the analysis.

Since creating reliable reviews of available publications will be a key success factor for providing effective policy briefs, some additional tools for this are referenced in the Annex to this document.

As a next step, the StandICT.eu 2026 project members and the FOREST committee should apply the methodologies mentioned in this report to produce ‘Deliverable D6.4 - Standardisation process & policy recommendations (Proof of concept process to accelerate EU standards development process)’ as well as ‘Deliverable D6.5 - Policy engagement strategy (Mechanism/Framework for engaging with Standards Policy and Strategy experts)’.

More generally, grouping together comments made throughout this report, the following recommendations are identified for prioritisation by policy makers:

- 1. Evaluate the Capacity of Existing European Standards Organisations (ESOs)**
 - a. Assess whether the current ESOs, namely ETSI, CEN, and CENELEC, have the adequate capacity and expertise to effectively handle IT standardisation in service of EU policy. This evaluation should consider the rapidly evolving nature of IT and digital technologies.
 - b. If the evaluation finds limitations in the current capacity or focus of ESOs, consider the advantages/disadvantages of establishing a new ESO specifically focused on IT, software and digital technology standardisation. This new organisation could address specific needs and challenges in the IT domain which may not be fully covered by existing ESOs, or be covered only in fragmented ways.
- 2. Review the New Legislative Framework (NLF) in the Context of Software Regulation and Products with Digital Elements**
 - a. Initiate a review of the New Legislative Framework (NLF) to assess its applicability and effectiveness in the context of software products and products with digital elements. This review should consider the unique characteristics and challenges associated with software, as distinct from isolated and static hardware products.

- b. The extension of the NLF to software (see the AI Act [118], Product Liability Directive [119] and Cyber Resilience Act [120]) presents new challenges and complexities that may not be fully addressed in the existing framework. Software, or products with digital elements, often involve rapid development cycles, continuous updates, and unique safety and security considerations.
- 3. **Revisit the EU Structures for Multi-Stakeholder Collaboration**
 - a. There are already regular, structured dialogues between different stakeholder groups, including the European Parliament, European Council, European Commission, National Standards Bodies, and societal stakeholders like consumers, employee unions, and disadvantaged groups. Examples of this are the Multi Stakeholder Platform on ICT Standardisation (MSP), currently being renewed, and the recently launched High Level Forum on European Standardisation [121].
 - b. However, additional stakeholder ecosystems currently not participating in these fora are relevant for ICT standardisation. The standout example is the open source ecosystem, both in terms of this innovation model's role in developing technical specifications and reference implementations, but also as a community of practice that will be subject to regulations and compliance standards. Their role in the policy conversations around standardisation needs more analysis.
- 4. **Review best practice in aligning public policy, research and standardisation**
 - a. Improving the alignment between EU policy, research activities and standardisation requires firstly a stocktaking of current best practice in an area which already has an extensive/fragmented body of discourse.
 - b. Choosing an initial theme from the overlap of EU research policy, the EC standardisation work plan and the policy priorities of the European Parliament would improve the chance of making effective recommendations.
 - c. When evaluating recommendations for changes, evaluate whether proposed government initiatives can hope to reduce identified market inefficiencies with a reasonable cost/benefit ratio.

5. ANNEX: TOOLS FOR STRATEGIC REVIEWS AND OVERVIEWS

5.1 Introduction

Most of the challenges which the FOREST committee will address have been considered before, at least partially. Therefore, as part of a chain of evidence supporting their recommendations, a systematic review of past work will usually be a prerequisite. This section considers a number of tools useful for collaboratively handling and documenting such reviews. FOREST members will need to consider which tools fit their needs, or seek others.

The author personally prefers using GoogleScholar, ELICIT and LitMap to obtain an overview of literature, managing the references using Zotero, simplifying some abstracts using ChatGTP+ if needed, then displaying mindmaps of the keyword-tagged results using Freeplane or Mindomo.

5.2 Literature Searching and Management

Google Scholar

GoogleScholar <https://scholar.google.com> allows using the google search engine to access scientific literature using the common boolean tools, for example “[systematic literature review](#)” (no quotes) generates 4 million hits, with several good choices on the first page. Results can be saved (using a star-shaped ‘save’ button next to each item) within a google account for later reading, or imported into Zotero (see below) for management of references.

ELICIT

Elicit <https://elicit.org> is a cloud-based research assistant using language models like GPT-3 to automate parts of researchers’ workflows. Currently, the main workflow in Elicit is Literature Review. If you ask a question, Elicit will show relevant papers and summaries of key information about those papers in an easy-to-use table, which can be downloaded in CSV format. The search can be refined. In July 2023 a fresh version beta.elicit.org was released, with additional functions to: (a) extra data from up to 50 pdfs, (b) get a table of concepts extracted from a set of papers, (c) connect to PDFs in your Zotero account, etc.

LitMap

LitMap <https://www.litmaps.com/> (a commercial service with some useful free aspects) can generate a map of cross-references of publications by beginning with

5.3 Reference Management

Zotero Reference Manager

Zotero www.zotero.org/support is an open-source (Linux, iOS or PC executable files, with local+cloud storage) reference management software that allows users to collect, organise, cite, and share research sources. It has browser plugins for Chrome, Firefox, and Safari, which allow users to save references and web pages with a single click. Users can import references from various sources such as library catalogues, databases, and websites (metadata), and organise them into collections for easy retrieval. It also provides tools for creating and formatting citations and bibliographies in various styles, including APA, MLA, Chicago, and it integrates into WORD. PDFs can be internally handled as files with highlighting, each highlight of which can be inserted into drafts as a copy-and-paste quotation with appropriate (name, year, page) reference. Zotero also allows users to collaborate and share their collections (links and/or copies) with others. The [groups feature](#) (private groups) allows you to share collections with colleagues on a project, etc.

5.4 AI Solutions for Summarising etc

ChatGPT+

ChatGPT <https://chat.openai.com/chat> is fine-tuned from GPT-3.5, a language model trained to produce text. ChatGPT was optimised for dialogue by using Reinforcement Learning with Human Feedback (RLHF) - a method that uses human demonstrations and preference comparisons to guide the model toward desired behaviour. Users are warned that their inputs continue to be re-used for training (i.e. are not confidential). It is quite useful for finding synonyms, rephrasing text and finding starting points for information ... but check everything. ChatGPT-Plus is a paid service that is reputedly better (fewer errors) and allows actions (e.g. summarization) on specifically uploaded documents.

5.5 Display of Systematic Reviews

Filtering or sorting a list of references (and abstracts) according to priorities just agreed during a group discussion (in the cloud) is a useful way to display results during a brainstorming session or to illustrate gaps in the literature. The following tools may be convenient for that, however the experience of the author is that different people absorb information more efficiently with one approach than another (see also [123]).

KUMU

KUMU www.kumu.io is a property graph web-based software (free on public web, \$9/mth/project for secure collaborations) with a highlyvisual interface: causal loop diagrams, stock-and-flow diagrams, stakeholder maps, actor maps...etc consisting of shapes connected by lines. This can make it excellent for some styles of presentations. Documents in any online platform (googledrive, oneDrive, Dropbox, Scribd etc) can be included as links. Import functions are available for Excel, from comma-separated values (CSV) file, or Google Sheets and other formats [124].

MURAL Whiteboard

MURAL <https://mural.co/> is an infinite whiteboard for teams, accessed in the cloud. Note that the export is limited to pdf style or CSV (for text notes only). See <https://support.mural.co/en/articles/4507081-download-objects-as-a-csv-file>

Mindmap Software

There are too many open source offerings to examine here, except by providing a few examples.

- MIRO Whiteboard <https://miro.com/>
- Freeplane <https://sourceforge.net/projects/freeplane/>
- MINDOMO <https://www.mindomo.com>

Below is a mindmap rendering of an excel file containing abstracts and links for nearly a thousand SDO and industrial organisations, sorted by main country of operation. The figure can be explored in the cloud [117]. Three organisations in France are expanded as examples below.

Figure 4: Mindmap of over 900 standardisation-related organisations, published on the Mindomo site [117]

5.6 Glossary and Taxonomy

A number of terms are cited here for convenience. The list can be expanded in future reports depending on the specialist topic areas.

- **‘de facto standard’** is a written document establishing technical specifications for goods, services, or processes, resulting from a consensus, and whose application is voluntary. It is designed to fulfil coordination functions through production and exchange. The term ‘voluntary standard’ is used in this document.
- **‘de jure standard’** is a written document establishing technical specifications for goods, services, or processes, resulting from a consensus, and whose application is mandatory within a given scope, as formalised through legal or regulatory processes.
- **‘European standard’** means a standard adopted by a European standardisation organisation i.e. CEN, CENELEC or ETSI [88]

- **‘European standardisation deliverable’** means any other technical specification than a European standard, adopted by a European standardisation organisation for repeated or continuous application and with which compliance is not compulsory [88]
- **‘European standardisation organisation’** means an organisation listed in Annex I of [88], i.e. CEN, CENELEC, ETSI
- **‘harmonised standard’** means a European standard adopted on the basis of a request made by the Commission for the application of Union harmonisation legislation [88] [125:8]. Note that “Compliance with a harmonised standard creates a presumption that products also comply with the essential requirements of the relevant EU legislation.”
- **‘ICT technical specification’** means a technical specification in the field of information and communication technologies
- **‘international standard’** means a standard adopted by an international standardisation body i.e. ISO, IEC or ITU [88]
- **‘international standardisation body’** means the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO), the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) and International Telecommunication Union (ITU) [88]
- **‘national standard’** means a standard adopted by a national standardisation body [88]
- **‘National Standardisation Body’** means a standards-making body notified to the European Commission by an EU Member State in accordance with Article 27 of [88]
- **‘notification’** is an act whereby an EU Member State informs the EC and the other Member States that a body, which fulfils the relevant requirements, has been designated to carry out conformity assessment according to a directive. There are mutual recognition agreements with EEA member states. [50]
- **‘Notified Bodies’** are nationally accredited bodies that examine the conformity evaluation of the production process completed on behalf of the manufacturers and whose correctness is certified according to uniform assessment factors. They must be notified by a Member State to the EC.
- **‘policy capture’** is the process of consistently or repeatedly directing public policy decisions away from the public interest towards the interests of a specific interest group or person. [126:9]
- **‘standard’** means a technical specification, adopted by a recognised standardisation body, for repeated or continuous application, with which compliance is not compulsory, and which is one of the following sub-types: international standard, European standard, harmonised standard or national standard [88]
- **‘technical specification’** means a document that prescribes technical requirements to be fulfilled by a product, process, service or system and which lays down one or more of the following: product/service characteristics and/or requirements such as quality, production processes [88]

- **'voluntary standards'** are standards developed or adopted by voluntary consensus standards bodies, both domestic and international. These standards include provisions requiring that owners of relevant intellectual property have agreed to make that intellectual property available on a non-discriminatory, royalty-free or reasonable royalty basis to all interested parties. [25] [127]
- **'voluntary consensus standards body'** is defined to have the following attributes: (i) openness, (ii) balance of interest, (iii) due process, (vi) an appeals process. [127]

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